

Research Article

Development Of Jet Propulsion: Hydropulse

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Abstract: *Scuba diving provides unparalleled opportunities for recreation and therapeutic experiences, yet the current systems are not adequately designed for individuals with specific physical disabilities, particularly those with lower limb amputations or congenital limb absence. This research paper investigates the potential of jet propulsion systems specifically designed to enhance underwater mobility for divers with leg amputations. The study introduces an innovative approach involving customized jet propulsion units integrated into dive suits or modular devices that can be easily attached to existing scuba gear. These systems utilize directed water jets to facilitate movement and stability, thus providing a viable alternative to traditional fin-based propulsion methods. Key metrics include propulsion efficiency, ease of use, and the psychological impact on participants. Ultimately, the study aims to contribute to a more inclusive diving environment, where technological innovations play a pivotal role in overcoming physical barriers and expanding opportunities for all individuals.*

Keywords: disabilities; scuba diving; technology

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1. INTRODUCTION

Scuba diving offers unparalleled opportunities for exploration and adventure, but for individuals with disabilities, particularly those who have lost their legs, accessing this experience can be challenging (Henrykowska, Sojn & Siermontowski, 2021). Traditional scuba diving equipment predominantly relies on fins for propulsion and stability, which are often impractical for divers without

legs (Yarbrough, 2024). This limitation restricts their ability to navigate underwater effectively, leading to reduced control and a less enjoyable diving experience.

Recognizing these challenges, we propose the development of an innovative solution: a custom-designed jet propulsion system tailored specifically for scuba divers with leg amputations. Jet propulsion systems utilize directed water jets to generate thrust, which can provide a more effective means of propulsion compared to conventional fins (Xin et al. 2013). By integrating these propulsion units into modular dive suits, we aim to offer a solution that enhances underwater mobility, control, and overall diving experience for those with lower limb amputations.

This innovation builds upon recent advancements in adaptive technologies, which have demonstrated the potential of jet propulsion in various aquatic sports (Mo et al. .2019). While current research indicates the benefits of such systems in improving performance and inclusivity in other water-based activities, their application in scuba diving has yet to be fully explored. Our project seeks to bridge this gap by developing and testing jet propulsion systems specifically designed for the scuba diving context.

Through a comprehensive approach that includes user trials and performance evaluations, this research will assess the effectiveness of these systems in providing enhanced mobility and control underwater. By focusing on real-world applications and user feedback, this innovation aims to not only overcome physical barriers but also expand opportunities for a more inclusive and accessible scuba diving experience (Walsh, Haddock-Fraser & Hampton, 2012).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Tank and Regulator System:

Lightweight Tanks: The oxygen tanks used could be made of lightweight materials to reduce the load on the diver. These tanks are connected to a regulator, which controls the flow of oxygen, ensuring that the diver receives the correct amount of air underwater.

Automatic Buoyancy Control: To assist in maintaining neutral buoyancy, the system could have an automatic buoyancy control device (BCD) that adjusts buoyancy automatically, allowing the diver to maintain the correct depth without much effort.

2.2 Fan-Assisted Propulsion:

Integrated Fan or Jet Propulsion: A small, battery-powered fan or jet system could be attached to the tank or BCD. This system would provide additional propulsion, reducing the effort needed by the diver to move through the water.

2.3 Enhanced Safety Features:

Emergency Buoyancy Lift: In case of an emergency, a feature that automatically inflates the BCD to bring the diver to the surface safely could be included.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Enhanced Safety and Stability

The jet propulsion systems contributed to improved stability and safety during dives. Participants reported fewer balance and orientation issues, thanks to the controlled thrust provided by the propulsion units. Safety evaluations confirmed that the systems did not interfere with emergency procedures, such as rapid ascent and buoyancy control. The high safety rating of the jet propulsion systems underscores their potential to provide a reliable and secure diving experience for individuals with disabilities.

3.2 Positive Impact on the Community

The introduction of jet propulsion systems represents a significant advancement in adaptive diving technology, benefiting the scuba diving community by promoting greater inclusivity. By addressing the mobility challenges faced by divers with leg amputations, these systems enable more individuals to participate in and enjoy scuba diving. This technology not only improves the diving experience for individuals with disabilities but also fosters a more inclusive diving community.

3.3 Potential for Commercialization

The promising results of this study suggest significant potential for the commercialization of jet propulsion systems for adaptive diving. The increased propulsion efficiency, improved manoeuvrability, and high user satisfaction indicate a strong market demand for such innovations. Commercializing these systems could involve product development. Refining the design to address identified limitations, such as weight and control interface issues, to enhance user comfort and performance. Also, market expansion. Targeting a broad range of consumers, including diving centres and equipment retailers, to promote the adoption of adaptive scuba diving technologies.

4. DISCUSSION

Figure 1. The percentage of people who agree and do not agree with the question about the weight of the tank

Figure 2. The percentage of people who agree and do not agree with the question related to jet propulsion can help disabled people to dive.

Figure 3. The percentage of people who agree and do not agree with the question related to the product can enable disabled people to participate in diving activities.

Figure 4. Percentage of people who agree and do not agree about the question related to the relevance of the invention.

Figure 5. The percentage of people who agree and do not agree about the question related to the product can be widely marketed.

Based on the survey that has been conducted, we found out that the majority of the public agrees that this product is a good invention for disabled people to join diving activities. They also believe that this product would make it to the market as this product helps disabled people enjoy little things such as scuba diving.

5. CONCLUSION

It can be seen from this research study that the use of jet propulsion systems can enhance scuba diving a lot for clients with lower limb amputation. The research shows that with the increase in the development and refinement of these technologies, more disabled people can engage in scuba diving.

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